

Comparison of the Path-weighted C_n^2 Derived from Time-lapse Imagery and Weather Radar

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Abstract— Irradiance based techniques are not suitable for profiling over long, nearly horizontal paths through atmospheric turbulence since they suffer from saturation effects. Alternate techniques that can provide reliable turbulence information over strong turbulence paths are currently being investigated. Two such approaches are introduced here. The first approach is a phase-based technique that uses the turbulence induced random motion in time-lapse images of a distant scene to estimate the path-weighted C_n^2 . An imaging experiment was conducted at the Air Force Institute of Technology to demonstrate this approach. A tripod-mounted digital camera captured images of a distant building every minute. Two different components of motion were apparent in the imagery: the random, faster motion due to atmospheric turbulence and the slower, vertical motion due to changes in the average refractive index gradient along the path. A correlation algorithm was used to measure the image shifts. The technique uses a derived set of path weighting functions that depend on the size of the imaging aperture and the patch size in the image whose motion is being tracked. The second method estimates C_n^2 values at different locations along a path using a combination of weather (NEXRAD) radar and numerical weather prediction (NWP) data. Two techniques have been used to derive the estimates. The first uses radar doppler information to determine the eddy thermal dissipation rate and combining this with NWP gradients to form a C_n^2 estimate. The second technique attempts to correct C_n^2 derived from radar clear-air reflectivity for noise and clutter and wavelength. The weights derived in the time-lapse imaging method have been applied to the noise and wavelength corrected NWP-radar derived C_n^2 profile to obtain the path-weighted value. The path-weighted estimates obtained using the optically-based, time-lapse imaging and weather radar-based methods have been compared. Both approaches show

great potential in estimating turbulence strengths over strong turbulence paths.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate characterization of atmospheric turbulence is critical for optimal design and performance assessment of adaptive optics systems in astronomical imaging, laser communications and tactical applications. Irradiance based methods such as the Scintillation, Detection and Ranging (SCIDAR) technique have been used in the past by astronomers to obtain a low resolution vertical profile of turbulence [1, 2]. Path-weighted refractive index structure constant, C_n^2 are traditionally measured using scintillometers, which comprise of calibrated lasers or points sources and specialized receivers [3]. However, irradiance based techniques are of limited use in the saturation regime and hence are not suitable for profiling

over long, nearly horizontal paths through turbulence. Additionally, related quantities such as C_v^2 and C_T^2 are measured using wind speed and temperature sensors and then used to derive C_n^2 [4]. But use of these methods requires physical sensors to be deployed in and around the region of interest. Alternate techniques that can provide reliable turbulence information over strong turbulence paths are being investigated [5]. Meier et. al. has demonstrated novel methods to extract turbulence information from polar orbiting satellite data [6]. A phase based technique, built on a process known as the Difference in Differential Tilt Variance (DDTV) was introduced by Whiteley et. al. [7]. The technique required two receiver apertures and an accompanying focal plane camera at one end of the path and three point source beacons at the other end. The apertures were used to observe either a single point source or two individual point sources. Since differential tilt measurements are phase related, conventional propagation theory can be used even for strong turbulence paths, where the variance of irradiance saturates.

In the present work, two different methods for estimating path-weighted C_n^2 are introduced. The first method estimates the path-weighted C_n^2 from turbulence induced random motion in time-lapse images of a distant target. Since this method is based on tilt measurements, it is a phase-based technique. The second approach uses a combination of Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) and Next-Generation Weather Radar (NEXRAD) data to get turbulence information along the path. The immense volume coverage provided by NEXRADs and NWP forecast models provide an advantage over the limited coverage provided by other sensor systems. The cost advantage of using freely available data over instrumentation is obvious. While the radar itself is an active device, their data are publicly available for download, so using weather radar and forecasts to measure C_n^2 has the added benefit of being a "passive" method.

The next section on methodology discusses the two approaches. The time-lapse imaging experiment and the path weighting functions are presented in the first part of this section. The second part of the methodology section outlines two different techniques for estimating turbulence strengths along the path using NWP and NEXRAD data. The first, estimates C_n^2 along the optical propagation path using Tatarskii's method applied to Ciddor's equation for refractivity [8, 9]. In this method, gradients of passive additives are determined from NWP gridded data, and NEXRAD radar. The second technique for estimation of C_n^2 uses values of C_n^2 derived from NEXRAD clear-air reflections and a baselining technique to account for non-turbulent scatterers and the disparity in response of index of refraction, n , at the NEXRAD's 10 cm wavelength, and the visible light wavelength (represented as 500 nm). Results from the time-lapse imaging experiment and the NEXRAD-NWP based techniques are compared in Section 3. A brief summary of our findings is given in Section 4.

2. METHODOLOGY

Time-lapse Imaging

A schematic of the experimental arrangement is shown in Fig.1. The experiment was conducted from the Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT) over 2 weeks in the month of July 2014. An imaging system, comprising of a Canon 40D digital camera (pixel pitch 5.7 μm) and a telephoto lens with focal length 300 mm (system # 5.6) was used to image the Good Samaritan Hospital building located 8 miles (12.8 Km) away. The camera was mounted on a sturdy tripod and was pointed through a window on the first floor of AFIT. A cardboard shield was used to shade the tripod from direct sunlight. The camera and the building were at almost the same elevation; hence the path through turbulence was nearly horizontal.

Figure 1. Schematic of the experimental setup.

Figure 2 shows a ground elevation plot from AFIT to the hospital with a valley drop of about 60 m between the two sites. An image was captured every minute and directly written to a laptop computer. A cross correlation algorithm was used to estimate the image shift. The images were first cropped to roughly isolate the building and a Gaussian window was applied to the images to reduce the effects of the frame edges on the correlation result. The cross correlation was performed between adjacent images in the sequence and a parabolic fit was applied to the correlation peak to provide a sub-pixel estimate of the shift between images. Example images taken at different times during the daytime hours on July 25, 2014 are presented in Fig. 3. The vertical and horizontal shifts calculated from the correlation algorithm are shown in Fig. 4.

Two different components of image motion are apparent in Fig. 4. The plot of the vertical shifts suggests that over the course of the day, the hospital seems to drop by about 4 meters (m). This is expected, as the temperature inversion that built up during the night disappears during the day, causing a reduction in the refractive index gradient. In the early evening, the building seems to move upwards. The vertical drift during the daytime is slow and is due to variations in the path-averaged index gradient. The net motion in the horizontal direction is small; this slight bias is possibly due to differential heating of the tripod. In addition

to the slow motion in the vertical direction, both the vertical and horizontal motion plots show a random, faster image motion which can be attributed to atmospheric turbulence. In the present analysis, the variance of the turbulence-induced image motion is used to estimate the path-averaged C_n^2 .

Figure 2. Experimental path with surface elevation profile. The hospital is on the left and AFIT on the right in the elevation plot.

Figure 3. Images from July 25, 2014. Image capture times are (a) 07:00 EST, (b) 11:00 EST, (c) 15:00 EST and (d) 19:00 EST.

Figure 4. Frame to frame image motion computed from July 25 images. (a) Vertical motion and (b) horizontal motion.

Path Weighting Functions

Expressions for the path weighting functions have been developed earlier in [10]. However, some of the development is shown here for the convenience of the reader.

The z -tilt over an aperture of diameter D , when viewing a source in the direction θ can be expressed as [11],

$$\alpha(\theta) = \frac{32\lambda}{\pi^2 D^4} \int d\mathbf{r} W(\mathbf{r}) \mathbf{r} \phi(\mathbf{r}, \theta), \quad (1)$$

where λ is the wavelength, $\phi(\mathbf{r}, \theta)$ is the turbulence induced wavefront distortion at aperture coordinate \mathbf{r} and

$$W(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} 1 & |\mathbf{r}| \leq 0.5D \\ 0 & |\mathbf{r}| > 0.5D. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The mean correlation between tilts observed at the aperture due to two sources at viewing directions θ_1 and θ_2 can be written as,

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \alpha(\theta_1) \cdot \alpha(\theta_2) \rangle \\ &= \left(\frac{32\lambda}{\pi^2 D^4} \right)^2 \left\langle \iint d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' W(\mathbf{r}) W(\mathbf{r}') \mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{r}' \phi(\mathbf{r}, \theta_1) \phi(\mathbf{r}', \theta_2) \right\rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where the angled brackets indicate ensemble averaging.

For a spherical wave propagating a distance L through turbulence characterized by the Kolmogorov power spectrum, it has been shown in [10] that (3) reduces to,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \langle \boldsymbol{\alpha}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2) \rangle \\
&= \left(-\frac{2.91}{2} \right) \left(\frac{16}{\pi} \right)^2 D^{-1/3} \int_0^L dz C_n^2(z) \int_0^{2\pi} d\vartheta \\
& \int_0^1 du \left[(u \cos^{-1} u) - u^2 (3 - 2u^2) \sqrt{1 - u^2} \right] \\
& \left[u^2 \left(1 - \frac{z}{L} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{z}{D} |\boldsymbol{\theta}_1 - \boldsymbol{\theta}_2| \right)^2 + 2u \left(1 - \frac{z}{L} \right) \left(\frac{z}{D} |\boldsymbol{\theta}_1 - \boldsymbol{\theta}_2| \right) \cos \vartheta \right]^{5/6}.
\end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The receiver is located at $z = 0$ and the source is located at $z = L$. Each pixel in the time-lapse imagery corresponds to a patch of approximately 0.24 m, not just a point on the target. Hence the shift (or the tilt) measured from the whole image, or even a pixel in the image is not tilt due to a single point source, but rather an average tilt due to several incoherent point sources over a patch. Since a Gaussian window is applied to the images before the cross-correlation is computed, to make the analysis consistent, the source patch is modeled as the same Gaussian. The patch-averaged tilt $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_p$ is defined as,

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_p = \frac{\int d\boldsymbol{\theta} \boldsymbol{\alpha}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) P_G(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\int d\boldsymbol{\theta} P_G(\boldsymbol{\theta})}, \quad (5)$$

where $P_G(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = e^{-\frac{4\theta^2 L^2}{d^2}}$, d being the 1/e patch diameter and $\theta = |\boldsymbol{\theta}|$. Hence, the patch-averaged tilt variance is,

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\alpha}_p^2 \rangle = \frac{\int \int d\boldsymbol{\theta}_1 d\boldsymbol{\theta}_2 \langle \boldsymbol{\alpha}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2) \rangle P_G(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) P_G(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2)}{\int \int d\boldsymbol{\theta}_1 d\boldsymbol{\theta}_2 P_G(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) P_G(\boldsymbol{\theta}_2)}. \quad (6)$$

Substituting (4) in (6), and performing several steps of integration as shown in [10], (6) reduces to:

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\alpha}_p^2 \rangle = \int_0^L dz C_n^2(z) f_\alpha(z), \quad (7)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
f_\alpha(z) &= -5.82 \left(\frac{16}{\pi} \right)^2 D^{-1/3} \int_0^\infty dx (x e^{-2x^2}) \\
& \int_0^{2\pi} d\vartheta \int_0^1 du \left[(u \cos^{-1} u) - u^2 (3 - 2u^2) \sqrt{1 - u^2} \right] \\
& \times \left[u^2 \left(1 - \frac{z}{L} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{zd}{DL} x \right)^2 + 2u \left(1 - \frac{z}{L} \right) \left(\frac{zd}{DL} x \right) \cos \vartheta \right]^{5/6}
\end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

is the path weighting function. It is to be noted that the weighting function for a point source is recovered by letting $d \rightarrow 0$ in (8).

No simpler form for the weighting function could be obtained, and hence in the present work (8) was evaluated numerically for cases of interest. Figure 5 shows a plot of $f_\alpha(z)$ for different patch sizes on the target. The aperture size and the path length used in the evaluation were the same as those used in the experiment, i.e. $D = 53.6$ mm and $L = 12.8$ Km. The weight is maximum at the receiver and drops down to zero at the target. This implies that the turbulence near the target hardly affects the image shifts seen by the camera. It is also apparent from Fig. 5 that the larger the size of the patch being tracked, the smaller the variance of the motion. This is unsurprising, as each subarea within a patch can have larger, random motion, but these random motions often average to a considerably smaller net motion for the patch. The tilt variance, seen by even a single pixel ($d = 0.24$ m) in the image is significantly less compared to that for a point source.

Figure 5. Path weighting functions for different patch sizes. The 0.24 m diameter patch corresponds to a single pixel in the image.

In this work, the path-weighted C_n^2 estimate was derived from the motion of the whole image. A Gaussian window with a 1/e diameter of 35 m (144 pixels) was applied to each of the cropped daytime images of July 25. The image motion, in pixels, from one image to the next was computed using the cross-correlation algorithm mentioned before. The shifts between neighboring images for the first 60 images (or 1 hour window) were used to calculate the shift variance. Next, the 1 hour observation window was moved by one image, i.e. the 1st image was dropped and the 61st image was added to the window and the analysis was repeated, resulting in a new variance. This procedure was continued until the last 60 images in the dataset were analyzed. Since the time interval between consecutive images was one

minute, the motion from one image to the next was attributed wholly to turbulence, and not refractive index gradient changes, which were observed to occur on a longer time scale. This was verified by repeating the analysis between an image and its next nearest neighbor instead of its nearest neighbor, and the results in the two cases were largely the same.

Assuming that the motion from one image to the next is independent, the angular tilt variance $\langle \mathbf{a}_p^2 \rangle$ in squared-radians (rad^2) can be obtained in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \alpha_H^2 \rangle &= 0.5 \left(\frac{\Delta p}{f} \right)^2 \langle I_H^2 \rangle \\ \langle \alpha_V^2 \rangle &= 0.5 \left(\frac{\Delta p}{f} \right)^2 \langle I_V^2 \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\langle \alpha_H^2 \rangle$ and $\langle \alpha_V^2 \rangle$ are the horizontal and vertical components of angular tilt variance, respectively, Δp is the pixel pitch in the camera, f is the focal length of the camera, and $\langle I_H^2 \rangle$ and $\langle I_V^2 \rangle$ are the variances computed from frame-to-frame motion (in units of squared-pixels) in the horizontal and vertical directions, respectively. Then,

$$\langle \mathbf{a}_p^2 \rangle = \langle \alpha_H^2 \rangle + \langle \alpha_V^2 \rangle \quad (10)$$

The 0.5 multiplier used in (9) converts the variances obtained from frame-to-frame motion to variances of actual image shifts. The path-weighted estimate of C_n^2 from (7) is:

$$C_{n,est}^2 = \frac{\langle \mathbf{a}_p^2 \rangle}{\int_0^L dz f_\alpha(z)} \quad (11)$$

C_n^2 values from NWP and NEXRAD data

Comparison C_n^2 data are created using a combination of Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP) and Next-Generation Weather Radar (NEXRAD) data and the process outlined in [12]. Two methods of estimating C_n^2 from NEXRAD and NWP are compared. The first, estimates C_n^2 along the optical propagation path using Tatarskii's method applied to Ciddor's equation for refractivity [2, 3]. In this method, gradients of passive additives are determined from NWP gridded data, and NEXRAD radar. Because this method produces an estimate which is strongly determined by NWP, it will be denoted as $C_{n,NWP}^2$. The second method for estimation of C_n^2 uses values of C_n^2 derived from NEXRAD clear-air reflections and a *baselining* technique to account for non-turbulent scatterers and the disparity in response of index of refraction, n , at the NEXRAD's 10 cm

wavelength, and the visible light wavelength (represented as 500 nm). Because this method's estimate more strongly weights the influence of the radar, it will be denoted $C_{n,NEXRAD}^2$. In both cases, estimates of C_n^2 are generated for the volumes of atmosphere, *bins*, sampled by the NEXRAD radar. Both methods will be briefly described, followed by a discussion of the path weighting issues.

Figure 6. NEXRAD reflectivity from the Dayton, Ohio region. Colored blocks represent reflectivity value. Red lines are major highways. The yellow line indicates the 12 km path from the Good Samaritan Hospital (circle) to AFIT (diamond). Black areas indicate no measurable reflectivity. Image generated using NOAA Weather and Climate Toolkit [13].

Global Forecast System (GFS) NWP data were used in this case to estimate potential temperature and potential vapor pressure gradients. The GFS horizontal grid spacing is 0.5°, which corresponds to a spacing of over 40 Km between grid points at the latitudes involved. Vertical resolution in the GFS is much finer. The vertical coordinates are pressure-coordinates with values decreasing from 1000 mb in 25 mb increments in the lowest portion of the Troposphere (from 1000-800 mb). The 25 mb spacing corresponds to spacing which varies from 200-300 m. Temporal resolution is 3 hours for the GFS forecast. For the time-lapse imaging path, it can be seen that the NWP data is very coarse.

Radar data are available on a 5-10 minute cycle depending on the radar scan mode. The operation radar mode is chosen to accommodate weather conditions within the radar's operational footprint [14]. While this temporal spacing is still coarse when compared to the time-lapse Imaging technique, it is significantly better than that provided with NWP. Spatial resolution of the radar allows for sub-path resolution, with up to 53 bins coinciding with the time-lapse imaging path. In order to estimate C_n^2 , the radar data are combined with NWP data to generate a C_n^2 estimate for each radar bin which coincides with the propagation path. For this path the first Fresnel zone radius may be up to 1 cm and radar bins are approximately 250 x 500 x 500 m. Because the first Fresnel zone is much smaller than the bin

size, the path is approximated as a line extending from the hospital to the camera, as shown in Fig. 6. Bins which this line passes through are considered to coincide with the path. The estimated C_n^2 along the path, thus becomes a piecewise constant function, $C_n^2(l)$.

For both methods, many of the bins along the path have no usable data. This creates a difficulty in deciding how to apply the path weighting function, $w(l)$. With l representing the normalized path distance parameter, and $C_n^2(l)$ to be the NEXRAD/NWP-estimated C_n^2 along the path, the path weighted C_n^2 should be

$$\langle C_n^2 \rangle = \int_0^1 w(l) C_n^2(l) dl. \quad (12)$$

While this is expected to work well in instances where $C_n^2(l)$ is defined over the interval $0 < l \leq 1$, it is unclear how to handle weighting the portions of the path with no data so that the path-weighted C_n^2 estimate is most likely to match that derived using time-lapse imaging. Choices which were considered include interpolating the missing data, and adjusting path weighting. Interpolation using linear or higher-order methods is difficult as missing data is often missing from either end of the path, and extrapolation could lead to unrealistic values. Additionally, the lack of a return may indicate turbulence below the threshold of detectability. Interpolation would thus artificially increase the path-weighted C_n^2 estimate. A constant value for C_n^2 could be used to interpolate the missing data. However, this choice is also problematic as it would artificially increase or decrease the estimate. Instead of the interpolation method, an adjusted path weighting function is applied. Let

$$p(l) = \begin{cases} 1 & C_n^2(l) \text{ exists} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}. \quad (13)$$

Then, the modified path weighting can be found as

$$\langle C_n^2 \rangle = \frac{\int_0^1 p(l) w(l) C_n^2(l) dl}{\int_0^1 w(l) p(l) dl}. \quad (14)$$

This solution disproportionately weights the path based on the availability of estimated C_n^2 data. In the case of only 1 value, (14) provides the same error as nearest neighbor interpolation. In the case of more values, (14) weights each available measurement in the proper proportion to each other. While use of (14) or interpolation of missing data both introduce error in the resulting path-weighted estimate of C_n^2 , method (14) is preferred because it does not incorporate any additional noise (from an arbitrary assumption about C_n^2 in missing bins) in the measurement.

In previous work, the path weighting function for comparison data was assumed to be uniform over the path [12]. While the uniform weighting does not match the actual instrument path weighting, it does simplify the choice of how to handle missing data.

Estimation method 1 is based on the two-thirds law for structure functions within a particular spectrum of sizes which was proposed by Kolmogorov for turbulence induced velocity perturbations and Obukov for passive additives [15, 16]. Tatarskii has shown that for well-developed turbulence, the structure function constant C_ϕ^2 for a passive additive, ϕ can be estimated from turbulence parameters and local gradients via

$$C_\phi^2 = a^2 \varepsilon^{-1/3} K_\phi \left(\frac{d\langle\phi\rangle}{dz} \right)^2. \quad (15)$$

In (15), a is a universal constant, ε is the rate at which Turbulent Kinetic Energy (TKE) is turned into heat, K_ϕ is the diffusion constant for ϕ and $d\langle\phi\rangle/dz$ is the local mean gradient. This method is commonly used to find C_n^2 by estimating $d\langle n \rangle/dz$ from local potential temperature gradients and $\partial n / \partial T$ under the assumption that $K_n / K_T \approx 1$ [5,8,12,14, 17-19]. This allows C_n^2 to be written in terms of C_θ^2 using the partial derivative $\partial n / \partial \theta$,

$$C_n^2 = \left(\frac{\partial n}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 C_\theta^2 = a^2 \frac{K_H}{K_M} L_0^{4/3} \left(\frac{\partial n}{\partial \theta} \frac{d\langle\theta\rangle}{dz} \right)^2, \quad (16)$$

where L_0 is the outer scale of turbulence. The ratio of diffusion of heat to diffusion of momentum, K_H / K_M is set to 1 for small gradient Richardson number, $R_i < 0.01$ and is decreased via the Kondo equation [19],

$$\frac{K_H}{K_M} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{7R_i} & R_i \geq 1 \\ \frac{1}{6.873R_i + \frac{1}{1 + 6.873R_i}} & 0.01 < R_i < 1 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

for $R_i \geq 0.01$.

The method is further modified in two ways. First, rather than using the common RF refractivity equation,

$$N = (n-1) \times 10^6 = \frac{79}{T} \left(P + \frac{4800e_v}{T} \right), \quad (18)$$

where T is temperature in K, P is pressure in mb, and e_v is water vapor pressure in mb, to find partial derivatives of n in the visible, Ciddor's equation is used instead [9],

$$N = \frac{PM_\alpha}{ZRT_0}(1-x_w) \frac{N_{\alpha s}}{\rho_{\alpha s}} + \frac{PM_w}{ZRT_0} x_w \frac{N_{ws}}{\rho_{ws}}. \quad (19)$$

This is appropriate as Ciddor's equation more accurately represents the response of index of refraction to local variations in temperature, pressure and water vapor [9] at visible wavelengths. A more convenient form of (19) for use in estimating C_n^2 is

$$N = \frac{P}{ZT}(A+x_w B) \quad (20)$$

where Z is the compressibility of moist air, x_w is the molar fraction of water vapor and A and B are wavelength dependent constants.

The second modification of (16) is the inclusion of non-hydrostatic pressure gradients, or the pressure gradients required to maintain circulation of turbulent vortices and potential vapor pressure $e'_v = (P_0/P) e_v$, where P_0 is the same reference pressure where potential temperature, θ is defined. Both have been shown to significantly increase agreement with scintillometer measurements taken over a year at a nearby Dayton site, and a site in Albuquerque, New Mexico [12]. In its extended form (16) becomes

$$C_n^2 = a^2 \frac{K_H}{K_M} L_0^{\frac{4}{3}} \times \left[\left(\frac{\partial n}{\partial T} \frac{d\theta}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial n}{\partial P} \frac{dP'}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial n}{\partial e_v} \frac{de'_v}{dz} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (21)$$

Here local gradients of potential temperature, θ and potential vapor pressure, e'_v are determined from NWP and turbulence induced non-hydrostatic pressure deviations, P' are determined from NEXRAD spectrum width, σ_v using the method presented in [12]. Spectrum width is used to determine TKE via the dissipation rate, ε using [14]

$$\varepsilon \approx \left[\frac{\sigma_v^3}{\sigma_r (1.35a)^{3/5}} \right] \left(\frac{11}{15} + \frac{14}{15} \frac{r^2 \sigma_\theta^2}{\sigma_r^2} \right)^{-3/2}, \quad (22)$$

where σ_r is the range gate spacing of the radar and σ_θ is the radar beamwidth. The energy spectrum can be determined from ε via Tatarskii's relation [8],

$$E(l) = a\varepsilon^{2/3} \left(\frac{2\pi}{l} \right)^{-11/3}, \quad (23)$$

where l is the vortex size. It is then possible to determine the pressure gradient via a circulation model. Here the Lamb-Oseen vortex model is used [20] to provide the radial velocity component of a cylindrical vortex. Using this

model, the pressure gradient required to maintain circulation can be shown to be [12]

$$\frac{dP}{dr} = \frac{\rho}{r^3} \left\{ \frac{\Gamma}{2\pi} \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{r^2}{r_c^2(t)} \right) \right] \right\}^2, \quad (24)$$

where ρ is the density of the air, r_c is the eddy core radius, and Γ is the circulation. Steady-state turbulence is assumed, so the mean eddy lifetime and circulation are determined from ε and the eddy size l , following [12]. Eddy size is chosen so that the core radius is similar in size to the traditional inner scale of a few cm. In this case, $l = 3$ m was chosen. This value showed good agreement throughout the summer for a nearby Dayton path, and corresponds to a core radius of about 3 cm.

This method often provides a complete path, because the pressure contribution to $d\langle n \rangle/dz$ is small. For this reason, it is possible to fill in missing bins with estimates based solely on NWP. Because the radar only provides a slight modification to the structure of the coarse-resolution NWP estimate, this method does not significantly leverage the increased resolution that NEXRAD provides.

The second method for determining C_n^2 uses radar reflectivity to calculate C_n^2 as presented in [12]. To estimate C_n^2 , radar reflectivity values are used with [5, 12]

$$C_n^2 = 2.63\pi^5 \lambda^{-11/3} |\kappa_w| \frac{10^{dBZ/10}}{1000^6}. \quad (25)$$

Following their convention, λ is the wavelength, κ_w is the complex index of refraction for water, and dBZ is the reflectivity. These values are shown to be much higher than measurements taken by visible or IR sensors. This disparity is due to a combination of effects [12,21], and is compensated for by applying a baselining technique such that the mean C_n^2 reported by the NEXRAD matches that of the NWP C_n^2 . To make the baseline correction, NWP C_n^2 values are computed for each radar C_n^2 measurement. Then the log of both the radar and NWP C_n^2 is low-pass filtered with a sliding mean. The difference between the filtered C_n^2 functions is then computed and added to the original radar C_n^2 .

$$C_{n,corrected}^2 = C_{n,radar}^2(t) - C_{n,radar}^2(t) * f_M(t) + C_{n,NWP}^2(t) * f_M(t) \quad (26)$$

Here the * symbol denotes discrete convolution and $f_M(t)$ is the filter function modeled as,

$$f_M(t) = \frac{1}{M} \text{rect}\left(\frac{t}{M} \right). \quad (27)$$

Here $M = 10$ was used. This produces a 50-90 minute (depending on radar scanning rate) sliding average.

3. RESULTS

In this section, the time-lapse imagery index of refraction structure constant results from 25 July 2014 are compared to C_n^2 output derived primarily from NWP and to C_n^2 obtained from NEXRAD reflectivity data baselined to NWP data along the 12.8 Km path. This initial comparison demonstrated the potential need for a further lower-atmospheric correction in the K_H/K_M values.

Figure 7 illustrates path-weighted C_n^2 derived from time-lapse imagery on July 25, 2014. The plot of C_n^2 in Fig. 7 does not show the typical cycle of C_n^2 evolution on a fair-weather summer day. The presence of cirrus clouds and light fog did not allow a pronounced C_n^2 drop at sunrise. Less cloudiness in the morning allowed for some ground heating and a mid-morning C_n^2 peak (~minute 300). More clouds—and even some light precipitation—occurred at midday, which forced an early afternoon minimum. Sunshine in after 2 PM allowed for the highest C_n^2 values of the day in the mid-afternoon around minute 550.

Figure 7. Path-weighted C_n^2 derived from time-lapse imagery on July 25, 2014.

Figure 8 shows the C_n^2 values derived primarily from NWP as described in the previous section. The time-lapse imaging weights have been applied to the C_n^2 values in each bin to get the path-weighted estimate. What immediately stands out in these plots—in both the originally calculated temporal resolution trace and the 5-point running average (referred to in the figure as “filtered C_n^2 ”) —is that the midday values of C_n^2 are roughly the same order of magnitude as those obtained with time-lapse imagery, but early morning and evening values are up to two orders of magnitude lower. The separate mid-morning and mid-afternoon C_n^2 peaks are discernible; however the mid-morning peak is stronger in this case.

Figure 8. C_n^2 derived from NWP with original K_H/K_M values.

Figure 9 shows the C_n^2 values derived from NEXRAD reflectivity with baselining to NWP as described in the previous section. The problem of several missing bins has been handled by applying uniform weighting instead of time-lapse imaging weights to derive the path-weighted C_n^2 . Again, like what is seen in Fig. 8, midday C_n^2 values are roughly same order of magnitude as those in Fig. 7, but early morning and late day values are orders of magnitude lower. Additionally, it is difficult to identify two distinct daytime peaks as are evident in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

Figure 9. C_n^2 derived from NEXRAD reflectivities with original K_H/K_M values.

The NWP data used to derive C_n^2 values in the NWP technique and to baseline the NEXRAD method, is obtained from the 0.5 deg resolution Global Forecasting System (GFS). The GFS is capable of inferring cloud layers and possible precipitation produced by those layers; however it does not have the horizontal and vertical resolution to accurately assess the full radiative transfer effects of those cloud layers. Thus the GFS does not accurately capture the effects of high overcast conditions on near-surface temperatures—it tends to allow such “thinner” cloud layers to transfer nearly as much energy through as if they were not present. This is perhaps why Figs. 8 and 9 show low non-daylight C_n^2 values and a distinct midday peak (as if there were no clouds).

Both the NWP and NEXRAD calculation methods are strongly dependent on the ratio K_H/K_M . Simply stated, this ratio describes how flat or spherical the turbulent eddies are.

In an afternoon boundary layer (approximately the lower 1500 m of the atmosphere), there are plenty of vertical motions so the ratio of eddy diffusivity of heat to eddy diffusivity of momentum is approximately 1. At night, or in stable periods when the temperature decreases with height significantly less than the adiabatic rate (9.8 K km^{-1}), the K_H / K_M ratio can drop to 0.01 or lower. It is proposed here that the NWP data from the GFS for the Dayton, Ohio region on 25 July 2014 allows the K_H / K_M values to fall too low given the alternating clear/scattered and overcast conditions. Thus a correction to the K_H / K_M values was implemented where the cuberoot of the K_H / K_M values was used in place of the original values. Taking the cuberoot maintains the afternoon K_H / K_M values near 1 as they should be, but increases the values to near 0.1 at times when the stability is such that it is not neutrally buoyant but it is not so stable that values as low as 0.001 are justified (e.g. high overcast periods that NWP has difficulty in characterizing).

Figures 10 and 11 demonstrate how NWP and NEXRAD C_n^2 techniques are modified with the cuberoot, $(K_H / K_M)^{1/3}$ values. In both cases, the morning and evening C_n^2 minima are brought much closer to the values seen in the time-lapse imagery plot (Fig. 7). Additionally, and perhaps most significantly, the cuberoot modification makes two daytime peaks in C_n^2 values discernible in both Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. Importantly, the mid-afternoon peak is now the higher peak in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11, as is the case in Fig. 7.

Figure 10. C_n^2 derived from NWP with modified K_H / K_M values.

Figure 11. C_n^2 derived from NEXRAD reflectivities with modified K_H / K_M values.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces three novel techniques for C_n^2 profiling over long, nearly horizontal paths. The first approach introduced is a phase-based technique that uses the turbulence induced random motion in time-lapse images of a distant scene to estimate the path-weighted C_n^2 . Two different components of motion were apparent in the imagery: the random, faster motion due to atmospheric turbulence and the slower, vertical motion due to changes in the average refractive index gradient along the path. A correlation algorithm was used to measure the image shifts. The technique uses a derived set of path weighting functions that depend on the size of the imaging aperture and the patch size in the image whose motion is being tracked. A second method estimates values at different locations along a 12.8 km path using a combination of NEXRAD radar and NWP data. Two techniques have been used to derive the estimates. The first uses radar doppler information to determine the eddy thermal dissipation rate and combining this with NWP gradients to form a C_n^2 estimate. The second technique attempts to correct C_n^2 derived from radar clear-air reflectivity for noise and clutter and wavelength. The weights derived in the time-lapse imaging method have been applied to the NWP and radar derived C_n^2 profile to obtain the path-weighted value. The path-weighted estimates obtained using the optically-based, time-lapse imaging and weather radar-based methods have been compared. Both approaches show great potential in estimating turbulence strengths over strong turbulence paths. The radar and NWP methods additionally offer the potential of assessing range-gated C_n^2 fields over large atmospheric volumes.

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